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GREEN PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT AND BALANCED SCORECARD: THE NIGERIAN CIVIL SERVANTS' EXPERIENCE

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Abstract: The need to promote efficiency and sustainability of any organization has resulted in the use of green human resource management practices as well as the balanced scorecard methodology. As the workers in federal civil service are obliged to promote efficiency, this work examined the level of use of green human resource management practices and balanced scorecard principles in selected ministries of the federal republic of Nigeria, using the descriptive survey design. It is interesting to discover that there is a predominant application of the green human resource management practices while the balanced scorecard methodology is still on a very marginal level. The study concludes that green performance management practices is very critical in any given establishment and that the use of balanced scorecard is still very minimal in the federal ministries studied, even though there are other evaluation measures for accessing the staff performance and overall output of the ministry. The study also concludes that the staff members especially the management level workers should ensure adequate integration of the green performance management practices in the respective ministries to boost productivity and efficiency. The study therefore recommends that recruitment processes of the ministry need to be transparent a more rewarding green practice of recognizing the staff members who distinguish themselves in various ways and a more robust application of the two critical elements in all the ministries of the federal civil service.

Keywords: Green Performance, Green Human Resources, Balanced Scorecard, Civil servants

INTRODUCTION

Green performance management and balanced scorecard are two critical ingredients that have over the past years assisted managers to define principles and significant factors in different work environments (Kim, & Lee, 2018; Sandkuhl, & Seigart, 2019, Van Der Aalst, La Rosa, & Santoro, 2016). The Balanced Scorecard methodology is a managerial tool where all employees, from workers in production to the organization's management, can find their strategic aim and can meet it with the right strategic activities and measures (Dalla Via, Perego, & Van Rinsum, 2019). These suggest that a balanced scorecard can ordinarily entail the management system aimed at translating an organization's strategic goals into a set of organizational performance objectives that in turn, are measured, monitored, and changed. It can also involve a management system that provides feedback on both internal business processes and external outcomes to continuously improve strategic performance and results. It is a critical performance management system usually employed to ensure the effective achievement of the

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objectives of an organization (Arjunam et al., 2020), which is premised to help in the translation of strategic objectives into action plans and then linking them strategically with the objectives of the organization (Sharaf-Addin, & Fazel, 2023). The balanced scorecard has been argued to be helping to avert the short falls in any organization's traditional measures (Kaplan & Norton, 1996).

However, green performance management is comprised of policies, practices, and systems, that regard employees as green for the benefit of the natural environment, business, individuals, and the society at large (Renwick, Redman & Maguire, 2013). Green human resource management through its various specific practices defines an organization's alignment towards the protection of the environment (Sharaf-Addin, & Fazel, 2023). Based on these debates, this work interrogated the use of Green Human resource management practices and balanced scorecard methodology among selected ministries in a federal civil service in Nigeria.

BACKGROUND OF STUDY

The term Green Human Resource Management (Green HRM) may be viewed as the integration of environmental management program into human resource management system of an organization, the process of aligning human resource management policies and practices strategically towards environmental friendly policies and practices which aims at reducing carbon footprint of each employee working in the organization providing them with healthy and motivated work culture (Subhadeep, Soumendra, Nabanita, & Urvashi, 2000).

Meanwhile, the Balanced Scorecard concept is a comprehensive tool in which each organizational unit must adapt its activities to achieve specific aims in relation to defining a business strategy (Slávik, & Zagoršek, 2016; Sasse, 2014). Individual business units in companies need to identify their measurements to link the four balanced scorecard perspectives which encompass: the perspective of internal processes, the customer perspective, the perspective of innovation and education, and the financial perspective (Sasse, 2014).

Each perspective is defined by setting strategic goals in the given field. For the strategic objectives, measures are chosen which serve as a basis for quantitative control. It is also necessary to choose strategic actions, through which the organization can reach the set goals. Strategic goals, measures, target values and strategic actions are mutually interconnected by linkages operating on a cause-effect principle. The tasks defined in this way form the basic principle of the Balanced Scorecard concept. (Cifalino, & Lisi, 2019; Kaplan, & Norton, 1992).

Besides, Balanced Scorecard helps visualize how the determined goals can be achieved and what success factors are necessary to reach the desired goals (Tabatabaei, Omran, Hashemi, & Sedaghat, 2017). The BSC concept enables companies to get feedback from each organizational unit related to their control, which will help the business to achieve better financial performance and the ability to innovate in individual organizational areas (Malagueño, Lopez-Valeiras, & Gomez-Conde, 2018).

Balanced Scorecard is a concept of how to transfer vision and strategy into goals and their metrics so that they comprehensively cover not only areas of the organization's financial performance, but also non-financial areas. The goals and measures are organized within the BSC into four perspectives which include financial, customer, internal processes and learning, and growth. The Balanced Scorecard is a tool of communicating mission and strategy between the various levels of management and ordinary employees. It is used to keep all workers informed about the activators that affect current and future success (Amin, & Romli, 2019; Asiaei, & Bontis, 2019). The concept of balanced scorecard is also connected with the creation of a strategic map, which will enable better reading of strategic goals and ways of achieving them in the form of graphical visualization. Both the short-

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term and long-term objectives need to be considered when developing the strategic map. These objectives should then be communicated to all organizational levels of an organization.

In fact, the absence of a connection between managers and objectives was identified when developing the Balanced Scorecard concept (Hristov, Chirico, & Appolloni, 2019; Lin, Hu, Tseng, Chiu, & Lin, 2016). The main mission of the Balanced Scorecard concept is that the organization is not managed according to the past but according to future-oriented strategies to secure its long-term existence. It is important to formulate a strategy that is comprehensive and covers all business areas so that it is specific and transparent and touches all specific works. When choosing the right goals and measures, and choice of objectives, Balanced Scorecard can guide the organization's behavior complaint with the strategy since goals affect behavior. The main meaning of the Balanced Scorecard concept is that strategic goals and their representation are at the forefront. Strategic goals are derived from a vision and strategy and thus become strategically important goals of the organization deciding on its overall success. To plan and monitor their achievement, it is necessary to assign the corresponding financial and non-financial indicators to these objectives and the target and actual values of these measures. The strategic actions that are assigned to each objective should ensure that the objectives are achieved. Therefore, each strategic action has a given deadline, budget, and a specific responsible person (Hermawan, & Anshari, 2016; Manville, Karakas, Polkinghorne, Petford, 2019; Alsharari, Eid, & Assiri, 2019)

It is therefore understood that the main objective of the balanced scorecard concept is to rectify the constraints of traditional performance measurement tools, as well as to transform business strategies into key performance indicators (KPI) to ensure a balance between short-term performance measured through financial indicators and non-financial factors that should head the organization towards better competitiveness and long-term sustainability (De Felice, Petrillo, & Autorino, 2015; Brunswicker, & Vanhaverbeke, 2015). The model identifies optimum values that are used as crucial elements to attain overall performance. This model then combines the intangible elements of performance measurement, which are vital for many organizations (Korenková, Závadský, & Lis, 2019). The methodology of the traditional balanced scorecard has evolved towards a business sustainability balance sheet which has integrated institutional, economic, socio-cultural, and environmental perspectives. In terms of sustainability, the balanced scorecard determines a causal connection between business factors to set priorities and objectives in a rational process of making decisions (Giannoukou, & Beneki, 2018).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Organizational effectiveness through GHRM and balanced scorecard are two critical elements that have become very vital for all institutions/firms. The extent to which organization incorporate the GHRM practices and the balanced scorecard methodology requires an empirical search for obvious reasons. This is since some organizations may be found wanting in some critical areas despite the privileges attainable using GHRM practices and balanced scorecard methodology. This works this work therefore interrogates the level of use and an applicability of the GHRM practices and the balanced scorecard methodology in federal establishments.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this study was to ascertain the experience of the Nigerian Civil Servants on the use of green performance management and balanced scorecards. The Specific Objectives of the Study include:

- i. To determine the level of use of performance management practices among Nigerian civil servants.
- ii. To find out the level of use of balanced scorecards in measuring performance among the Nigeria civil servants.

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ii. To determine the effect of green performance management practices among the ministries in the Nigerian civil service.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

This study addressed the following research questions:

- i. What is the level of use of performance management practices among Nigerian civil servants?
- ii. What is the level of use of balanced scorecard in measuring performance among the Nigeria civil servants?
- ii. What are the effects of green performance management practices among the ministries in the Nigerian civil service?

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study is of a practical significance as it will help identify the various ways the GHRM practices and balanced scorecard are practicable within the deferral government ministries in Nigeria.

The study will also be of theoretical significance as to will confirms the applicability of the AMO theory and how it is either upheld or debunked in this work based on the prevalent findings.

The study will also remain significant as it focuses on only the federal government owned ministries in Nigeria as against other previous studies that dwelt on private firms and establishments.

The study will also remain significant as relevant bodies and institutions will rely on the findings to make recommendations regarding possible adoption and use of the GHRM practices and the balanced scorecard in their establishments.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The study is limited to only to key issues or variables (Green Human Recourse Management Practices and Balanced Scorecard)

The study is solely focused on some selected ministries of the Nigerian federal Civil service.

In terms of methodological scope, the study employed the descriptive survey, which is an aspect of the quantitative research design. However, the questioned served as the instrument for data collection.

LITERATURE REVIEW

CONCEPTUAL REVIEWS

Green Performance Management

Hamod and Majeed (2021) explained that the term green human resource management practice has become most common in business, and its importance increases over time. This term also has a secured position as a hot topic in modern research work as awareness of environmental management and sustainable development is increasing day by day all over the world. The topic of green human resource management practices not only includes awareness of environmental affairs, but also the social and economic wellbeing of both the organization and employees within a broader perspective (Hamod & Majeed, 2021). Sobaih (2020) defined green human resource management practice as the usage of human resource rules to support the sustainable use of property resources and to guarantee environmental sustainability. Sobaih (2019) defined green employee relations to include employee involvement and participation in green suggestion schemes and problem-solving, developing training courses for the union representatives in environmental management and cooperating with stakeholders in all environmental issues. Sobaih (2019) also viewed green discipline management as part of green human resource practices that ensure green employee behavior inside the organization are known and strictly adhere, to achieve the objectives and strategies of environmental management. These show that employee green performance

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management involves the practice of evaluating and improving capabilities of individuals and teams by enhancing their professional skills and environmental performance standards which help to achieve the goal of their organizations.

Several authors have looked at the concept of Green human resource practices, and balanced scorecard (Chayanan, 2020; Edeh & Okwurume, 2019, Bag & Gupta, 2019; Amran, Hung Kee, Nejati, & Yusoff, 2018; Islam, 2019; Eric & Odock, 2017) based on their efficacy and established some kinds of relationships among them. Mwitwa (2019) defined green human management practice as a process of making use of human resources at workplaces in order to achieve organizational goals with deliberate efforts to make sure the process contributes towards environmental sustainability. It intends to use human relations functions, strategies and practices as mechanisms for environmental management at workplaces. Also, Uddin and Islam (2015), explained the green human resource practices as an environmentally-friendly human resource policies and practices that on the one hand, help organizations achieve its monetary goal through environmental branding and, on the other hand, protect environment from any negative impact that might be caused by the policies and actions of the organizations.

Green Work Life Balance (QWL)

Jayashree and Selvarani (2019) defined green work-life balance as the green HR initiatives that are aimed at creating sound occupational health and organizational health. It encompasses two major elements, and they include operational efficiency and sustainability. Green work life balance practices are commendable because they help sustain the intellectual capital in any organization and can be instrumental in creating enhanced quality of work life (QWL) for both the employee and employer at large. There is a growing need for examining the impact of green work life balance towards operational efficiency. Green work life balance policies focus on employees' twofold roles as consumers and producers, because employees learn and practice environmentally relevant behavior in these two roles. Operational efficiency is influenced by green HR practices at their workplace and shaped by their green work life balance (GWL) perceptions (Ahmad, Kamaruddin, Mat, Mohd -Salleh, Nik, & Omar, 2018). Babin Dhas and Karthikeyan (2015) viewed work-life balance as an act of managing between paid work and other activities that are important to the employee - including spending time with family, taking part in sport and recreation, volunteering or undertaking further study. Boer, Gagnano, Miglioretti and Simbula (2017) defined work health balance as a state in which the worker feels there can effectively balance health and work needs, considering the management attention to the employees' health and the perception of compatibility between the personal health situation and the job characteristics.

Efficiency

Neil (2019) defined efficiency as the proficiency of a corporation to curtail the unwelcomed and maximize resource capabilities so as to deliver quality products and services to customers. There are several techniques and strategies that have been adopted to accomplish the basic goal of delivering quality goods and services to clients in the most cost-effective and timely manner. Resource utilization, production, distribution, and inventory management are the most common aspects of efficiency. Ndolo (2015) indicated that efficiency is the key determinant of the long-term solvency of businesses, micro-economic or firm-specific predictors of corporates' financial health. However, efficiency also has a direct impact on the profit margins of organizations; operational efficiency is often achieved by streamlining firms' core processes in order to effectively respond to continually changing market forces in a more cost-effective manner. In other words, firms can attain operational efficiency

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by minimizing redundancy and waste while leveraging their resources that contribute mostly to their success; and also, utilizing the best of their workforce, technology and business processes (Vangie, 2019).

Silbert (2018) opined the characteristics of efficiency are not just about the performance of the organization, although that certainly is part of it. An efficient organization can be described as one that usually spends fewer resources to produce the desired profit or outcome they seek. Efficiency has a lot to do with people's management in an organization, pushing responsibility to lower levels of an organization, making processes smoother and more efficient, and teaching managers to empower employees to take risks and find new solutions all have an immense impact on the speed and efficiency of the organization.

Vangie (2019) noted that reduced internal costs that result from operational efficiency help firms to be more successful in highly competitive markets, thereby achieving higher profit margins. The connection between operational efficiency and firms' financial performance has been widely studied. Inferences made drawn from these studies are however at variance. Macaulay (2017) emphasized that the advantages of efficiency are goods or services are created or delivered faster, cheaper, better, fresher, with few defects. Efficiency gains may be so great and justification for investment; however, user satisfaction is always important.

DEFINITION OF TERMS

Balanced Scorecard:

Balanced Scorecard is the management system aimed at translating an organization's strategic goals into a set of organizational performance objectives that in turn, are measured, monitored, and changed.

In this work, balanced scorecard entails the management system involving the activities taken by the ministries in Nigerian civil service towards translating the goals of the ministry into performance.

Green performance Management:

The Green performance management is comprised of policies, practices, and systems, that regard employees as green for the benefit of the natural environment, business, individuals and the society at large.

In this work, green performance management involves the policies, practices, and systems, that regard employees of the Nigerian civil service as green for the benefit of the natural environment, business, individuals, and the society at large

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The study is limited to only the green performance management and balanced scorecard methodology.

The study is also centered on only the Nigerian civil servants who work in the various federal government ministries.

The study is challenged by time, hence the need to limit the work to only the staff members of the Nigerian civil service.

THEORETICAL EXPOSITION

The study subscribed to the Ability, Motivation and Opportunity (AMO) theory initially proposed by Bailey (1993). Appelbaum, Bailey, Berg, & Kalleberg (2000) revealed that the notion of Human Relations policies and practices can be grouped into ability, motivation or opportunity-enhancing categories and linked to improved performance through operational efficiency, agrees that the theory have become the standard reference in Human Relations Management discipline. Based on the model and drawing on the concept of high-performance work systems (HPWS), the model was later developed by Appelbaum, Bailey, Berg and Kalleberg (2000), and its

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acronym stands for the three elements that enhance together employee performance: individual ability (A), motivation (M), and the opportunity to participate (O).

Also, Supporters of the theory, (Wong & Aspinwall, 2005; Mooradian, 2006; Zahra, 2007; Yang, 2007) acknowledge that AMO (ability, motivation, opportunity) model is a widely accepted model in human resource management (HRM) literature and its linkages with firm performance through operational efficiency. Given the importance of cultural and human intentions and behavioral factors, the three key AMO factors: ability (training for workers), motivation (incentive systems) and opportunity (trust) enhance competitive advantage and operational efficiency.

The implication, however, is that employees need to have a green ability to perform in green ways and they should also have a higher degree of willingness to exert the needed effort to perform the job in green way or environment-friendly way with the help of their superiors and employer. Motivation is very important to help employee to performed better, it stimulates employees to perform and successful in their duties, to accomplish relevant established organizational objectives. Hence, relevant top managers of the organization develop programmes to stimulate their subordinates to perform green duties to accomplish objectives relating to greening. One can argue that the ultimate performance of green Human Resource Management and green work life balance on efficiency falls within the scope of AMO theory.

EMPIRICAL LITERATURE REVIEW

Mowaiye, Akpa, Akinlabi, and Magaji (2022) looked at the effect of green human resource management practices, green work life balance on operational efficiency of selected hospitality firms in Lagos and Ogun states Nigeria. The data collected through primary sources (questionnaire). The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics employing regression analysis. The study revealed that Green human resource management practices, and green work life balance had significant and positive effects on operational efficiency in hospitality firms in Lagos and Ogun States Nigeria

Ardiza, Nawangsari, & Sutawijaya (2021) examined the effect of Green Performance Appraisal, Green Performance Appraisal and Green Compensation and Organizational Citizenship Behaviour for the Environment/OCBE on employee performance in 2 groups of employees based on employee length of service. The research is quantitative using a survey method with a sample of 76 people and Data analysis was done using the using SEM with the Smart PLS program. This study proves that OCBE does not mediate the effect of Green Compensation and Rewards and Green Performance Appraisal on Employee Performance in groups of employees who have worked for <5 years. Meanwhile, for groups of employees who have worked for more than 5 years, OCBE only mediates the effect of Green Compensation and Rewards on Employee Performance.

Benková, Gallo, Balogová. and Nemeč, (2020) examined the factors influencing the use of the Balanced Scorecard methodology in measuring organization performance in the engineering sector. They had the objective of verifying the importance of using non-financial factors in managing businesses which was in connection to the use of the Balanced Scorecard methodology and verify the dependence between the methodology and the lack of human and financial resources for its usage. The research was conducted over a period of six months, based on hypotheses verified with using the Chi-square test. To identify the factors that hinder the usage of the Balanced Scorecard in the addressed enterprises, standard deviation was used. The main result of the research is a finding

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that there is a statistically significant relationship between the enterprises considering the non-financial indicators and the use of the Balanced Scorecard methodology to be important. The study also found out the existence of the dependence between the lack of these resources and the use of the Balanced Scorecard

Kuria & Mose (2019) looked at the effect of green human resource management practices on organizational effectiveness of Universities in Kenya. The study employed descriptive research design using a study population of ten universities in Kenya. The selected Universities have approximately 400 employees from the human relations office, deans of faculties/schools and senior managers. The study used purposive sampling to sample size 120 respondents who were selected from the selected universities. Semi structured questionnaires were used to collect primary data. The study revealed that green recruitment and selection, green human relations performance management, green training & development and green pay and reward recorded a positive and significant relationship with organizational effectiveness of Universities in Kenya.

Okechukwu (2017) carried out a study on the influence training, staff development and employee performance have on job satisfaction. The study found that a significant relationship exists among the variables, as staff training and development massively improves the performance of the workers.

Catherine (2016) conducted a study on how effective the green recruitment practices are on the Human Resources Executives in their IT sector. The study was able to conclude the establishment of a strong employment practices that will help in engaging the competent employees in an organization. The study, among others, suggested that adequate investment in employees of an organization has cumulative effects.

Brefo-Manuh (2017) carried out a study on the relationship existing between the appraisal of staff performance and their effectiveness in the organization. The study was a comparative analysis of private and public organizations within the Kumasi Metropolis. It was established from the study that the private and public universities studied, utilize the system of routine appraisal of performance in their attempt to improve productivity among members of staff. The study also established that their organizational efficiency is generally predicted by the appraisal system, justifying the need for other organizations to incorporate the routine culture of organizational appraisals for improved efficiency.

Bhutto (2016) conducted a study on how the green recruitment, training, and development impact on the performance of a firm in Pakistan. The study argued that many workers will always prefer to settle for green organizations, that such workers in Pakistan had an improved job satisfaction and commitment. They also shared the view that green practices need a constant monitoring to enable the organization to achieve an ecological sustainable management practice.

KNOWLEDGE GAP

The literature shows that there are gaps in examining the performance management system and balanced scorecard operations, simultaneously in the same study.

The literature also found a very noticeable gap in the aspect of examining the staff of the Nigerian civil service. However, the existing studies have heavily dwelt on recognized companies, firms, or industries while none had studied the staff members in the ministries of the Nigerian civil service.

SUMMARY OF LITERATURE REVIEW

Several authors (Chayanan, 2020; Edeh & Okwurume, 2019, Bag & Gupta, 2019; Amran, Hung Kee, Nejati, & Yusoff, 2018) found a positive effect among green human resource practices, green work life balance, organizational efficiency and balanced scorecard methodology. Eric & Odock (2017) established the effect of

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green human resources practices, green work life balance and operational efficiency for hotels adopt a variety of green practices in the areas of energy consumption, water consumption, waste generation, reduction and recycling and employee training and awareness creation. The author also found that there is a strong positive effect between green operations practices and operational efficiency, and that green operations practices are very important.

Chayanan (2020) found green human resources management practices, green work life balance such as perspective of human resources, benefits, performance management, employee relation work life balance are significantly influencing the operational efficiency of the organization. For environmental practices, environment management system, environmental training programs have a significant influence the operational efficiency of the organization. However, environmental supplied development does not influence the operational performance. It is therefore clear that green human resource practices and green work life balance are required for achieving the effective environmental performance and the GHRM practices and green work life balance are dependent on the ideal patterns of the green behaviors of the human resources managers, the integration of the environmental strategies in the firm's strategic goals leads to achieving an effective EMS. The researcher shed the lights on the HRM practices; because of its effectiveness in promoting the human capital and enhancing the operational efficiency and competitive advantage. Renwick et al, (2008 & 2013) found green training and development practices such as training staff to produce green analysis of workspace, application of job rotation to train green managers of the future, provision of specific training on environmental management aspects of safety, energy efficiency, waste management, and recycling, development of green personal skills, and re-training of staff losing jobs in relevant polluter industries.

It is also sacrosanct that green human resource management and green work life balance not only includes mindfulness towards environmental affairs but also stands for the social and economic well-being of both the organization and the employees. It can be used to reduce carbon footprints as well as costs, better efficiencies, make green awareness among the employees and initiate green work life balance programs (Nijhawan, 2014). Hence providing environmental education and enabling work life balance that can lead to a change in attitude and behavior of organizational members is very essential. Ahmad (2015) laid emphasis on providing such training to employees that can encourage recycling and waste management habits among them. Further, training staff to produce green analysis of workspace and energy efficiency, execution of job rotation to train green managers for future; and development of green personal skills can be considered as useful green training and development practices to enhanced operational efficiency (Maguire, Redman, & Renwick, 2013).

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

The design for the study is a quantitative design while the research method was used in carrying out the study is the descriptive survey.

AREA OF STUDY

The study is domesticated in Nigeria and among the staff of the federal civil service.

SOURCES OF DATA

The data for this work were sourced from both primary and secondary sources. Our primary source of data was made up of the first-hand responses obtained directly from the respondents through questionnaires, interviews, and observation. The secondary data were collected from the review of relevant documents, works and reports on

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the field of study which includes journals, magazines, newspapers, textbooks, reports, information gathered from internet and other authoritative books related to the topic.

POPULATION OF THE STUDY

For this research study, the population covered the staff of the federal ministries in Nigeria which is a total of 35,457 persons. This is illustrated in the table below.

Table 1

Population of staff of the federal government ministries spread across all the states of the federation.

S/N	Name of Ministry	Head Office	Population of staff across the states of the federation
1	Federal Ministry of agriculture and natural resources	Fed. Capital Territory Office Complex Block A, Area 11 (Eleven) P.M.B. 135, Garki, Abuja, FCT	1347
2	Federal Ministry of Aviation	Fed. Secretariat, ShehuShagari Way	696
3	Federal Ministry of Commerce & Tourism	Old Secretariat Area I, Block G & H P.M.B. 88, Garki, Abuja	1184
4	Federal Ministry of Information & Communications (including all FRCN and NTA stations)	Federal Secretariat, 2nd & 3rd Floors	3252
5	federal ministry of defence	Defence Headquarters Opp. Agura Hotel, P.M.B. 196, Area 7 Garki, Abuja	586
6	Federal Ministry of education & youth dev.	Federal Secretariat, Phase 2 (3rd Floor) ShehuShagari Way, Abuja	2892
7	federal ministry of environment	Federal Secretariat Complex 9th Floor, ShehuShagari Way PMB 468 Garki Abuja	1748
8	federal ministry for federal capital territory (m.f.c.t.)	Area 11, Garki, Abuja P.M.B. 25, Garki, Abuja	99
9	federal ministry of finance & economic development	(Opposite Central Bank) P.M.B. 14, Garki, Abuja	285
10	federal ministry of foreign affairs	Maputo St., Wuse, Zone 3 (Opposite Nigeria Custom Services), P.M.B. 130, Garki, Abuja	439

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11	federal ministry of health and social services	Block 4A (301-399), 3rd Floor New Fed. Secretariat Complex, Shehu Shagari Way, P.M.B. 83, (Garki Post Office), Abuja	3745
12	federal ministry of industries, trade and investment	P.M.B. 85, Garki Post Office, Old Federal Secretariat, Area 1, Garki Block 'C', Abuja	2253
13	federal ministry of culture tourism and national orientation	Phase II Federal Secretariat; Shehu Shagari Way Abuja Nigeria.	1674
14	federal ministry of internal affairs	Block 'F' Old Secretariat, Area I, Garki, Abuja P.M.B. 0016, Garki Post Office	69
15	federal ministry of justice	New Fed. Secretariat Complex 10th Floor, Federal Secretariat, Wing IB (1001-1099), Block One, ShehuShagari Way, Abuja	3952
16	federal ministry of labour and productivity	2nd Floor (257-237), Block 4A, New Federal Secretariat Complex, Shehu Shagari Way Central Area, Abuja	1862
17	federal ministry of petroleum resources	Federal Secretariat Shehu Shagari Way, Abuja	90
18	federal ministry of power & steel	New Fed. Secretariat Complex 3rd - 4th Floors, Annex B Shehu Shagari Way, Abuja	329
19	federal ministry of science and technology	9th Floor, New Fed. Government Secretariat (Opp. New Parade Ground), Shehu Shagari Way, Abuja	875
20	federal ministry of solid minerals development	5th Floor, Annex 3, New Federal Secretariat Complex, Shehu Shagari Way Central Area, Abuja	581
21	federal ministry of special duties	First Floor, Phase II, New Federal Secretariat Shehu Shagari Way, Abuja	461

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22	federal ministry of transport	2nd Floor, Annex 3, New Fed. Secretariat Complex Shehu Shagari Way, Central Area, P.M.B. 1136, Abuja	1243
23	Federal ministry of water resources & rural development	P.M.B. 159, Block 'A', Old Secretariat Area I Garki, Abuja	1095
24	federal ministry of women affairs and social development	2nd Floor (201-224), Annex 3, New Federal Secretariat Complex, Shehu Shagari Way P.M.B. 229, Central Area, Abuja,	1293
25	federal ministry of works and housing (f.m.w.&h.)	Radio House, Herbert Macaulay Way (South) P.M.B. ill, Garki, Abuja (Opp. Int'l. Conference Centre)	2649
26	federal ministry of youth & sport	New Federal Secretariat Complex, Maitama Sule, Garki, Abuja	758
TOTAL			35,457

SAMPLE SIZE

In determining the sample size for this research work, the researcher adopted a statistical formula by Taro Yamani to determine the sample size. The researcher chose 5% or 0.05 as the margin of error.

According to Taro Yamani (1964), to determine a sample size from the population.

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where n=sample size

N=total population size

1 is constant.

e = The assumed error margin or tolerable error which is taken as 5% (0.05)

Applying the above formula

$$n = \frac{35,457}{1 + 35,457(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{35,457}{89.6425} = 396$$

Therefore, the sample size is 396. Based on these, a total of three hundred and ninety-six copies of the questionnaire was administered to the respondents.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

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The researcher adopted a multi-stage sampling technique to select a total of twelve ministries out the existing twenty-six ministries. However, all staff of the selected ministries met on the spot, were sampled. The decision is hereby illustrated underneath:

Table 2
Sample of the ministries and Departments

S/N	Selected Ministries	No of respondents (Equal distribution or Sampling of the Staff in each selected Ministry)
1	federal ministry of agriculture and natural resources	33
2	Federal Ministry of Information & Communications (including all FRCN and NTA stations)	33
3	Federal Ministry of Education & Youth Dev.	33
4	Federal Ministry of Environment	33
5	Federal Ministry of Finance & Economic Development	33
6	Federal Ministry of Health and Social Services	33
7	Federal Ministry of Culture Tourism and National Orientation	33
8	Federal Ministry of Labour and Productivity	33
9	Federal Ministry of Science and Technology	33
10	Federal Ministry of Special Duties	33
11	Federal Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Development	33
12	Federal Ministry of Works and Housing (f.m.w.&h.)	33
	TOTAL	396

At the stage of the questionnaire distribution, an accidental sampling technique was adopted whereby the researcher sampled only the staff members in all the various departments who were available on their duty posts.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The data were self-administered by the researcher with the help of three research assistants.

FINDINGS AND CONCLUSIONS

THE LEVEL OF USE OF GREEN PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

The respondents were required to rank the statements on their level of use of green performance management. The results are as shown in Table 3.

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Table 3: The level of Use of Green Performance Management

Statement	Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
There is always a transparent recruitment exercise	15% (N=59)	21% (N=83)	6% (N=24)	27% (N=107)	31% (N=123)	100% (N=396)
There is improvement in staff motivation	33% (N=134)	30% (N=119)	6% (N=24)	9% (N=36)	21% (N=83)	100% (N=396)
Staff Members are well oriented with Green Performance Practices	36% (N=147)	27% (N=107)	- (N=0)	15% (N=59)	21% (N=83)	100% (N=396)
Staff Members participate in Green Performance Practices	45% (N=182)	27% (N=107)	21% (N=83)	6% (N=24)	- (N=0)	100% (N=396)
Staff members are regularly appraised	66% (N=265)	27% (N=107)	6% (N=24)	- (N=0)	- (N=0)	100% (N=396)

This table shows the level of use of green performance management practices among the members of staff of the selected ministries. The study found that the staff members in the selected ministries mainly disagreed (27%) and strongly disagree (30%) that there is always a transparent recruitment exercise. The implication is that there the recruitment exercise is not always transparent which is part of the green performance practices. The study further established the need for staff motivation. For instance, majority of the staff members agreed (33%) and also strongly agreed (30%) that there is need for them to be motivated. It is also significant to discover that quite a good percentage of them agreed (45%) and strongly agreed (27%) that the staff members of the ministries participate in their green performance practices. Many of them also agreed (66%) and strongly agreed (27%) that they are regularly appraised for promotions and advancements to enable them progress in their various cadres

THE LEVEL OF USE OF BALANCED SCORECARD METHODOLOGY

The respondents were required to rank the statements on their level of use of balanced scorecard methodology. The results are as shown in Table 4.

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Table 4: The Level Use of Balanced Scorecard Methodology

Statement	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
My ministry usually measures the staff performance	66% (N=265)	27% (N=107)	6% (N=24)	- (N=0)	- (N=0)	100% (N=396)
My ministry measures its overall performance	94% (N=371)	6% (N=25)	- (N=0)	- (N=0)	- (N=0)	100% (N=396)
My ministry adopts the use of balanced scorecard methodology	3% (N=13)	6% (N=24)	18% (N=70)	27% (N=107)	45% (N=182)	100% (N=396)
My ministry mainly utilizes other performance evaluation measures apart from the balanced scorecards	98% (N=388)	2% (N=8)	- (N=0)	- (N=0)	- (N=0)	100% (N=396)

This table documents the level of use of balanced scorecard methodology among the selected ministries. The study was able to discover that there is a very minimal use of the balanced scorecard methodology among the ministries as majority of the staff members disagreed (27%) and also strongly disagreed (45%) that the balanced score card is operational in their ministries. Instead, majority of them (98%) strongly agreed that their ministries mainly utilize other performance evaluation measures apart from the balanced scorecard methodology. However, majority of them also strongly agree (66%) and agree (27%) that the ministry usually measures staff performance, while almost all of them hold strongly (94%) that the ministry measures its overall performance.

EFFECT OF GREEN PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

The respondents were expected to rank the statements on the effect of green performance management practices. The results are as indicated in Table 5.

Table 5: the effect of green performance managements

Statement	Agree	Strongly Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Green performance practices enable me to do my job effectively and efficiently	33% (N=134)	30% (N=119)	6% (N=24)	9% (N=36)	21% (N=83)	100% (N=396)
Green performance Practices provide for a continuous training programme for my ministry staff	36% (N=147)	27% (N=107)	- (N=0)	15% (N=59)	21% (N=83)	100% (N=396)

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Green Performance management practices Provides for knowledge on matters concerning the environmental development	45% (N=182)	27% (N=107)	21% (N=83)	6% (N=24)	- (N=0)	100% (N=396)
The green knowledge/skills acquired from green training can be applied at workplace	66% (N=265)	27% (N=107)	6% (N=24)	- (N=0)	- (N=0)	100% (N=396)

As shown in this table, the study found that the respondents mainly agreed (33%) and strongly agreed (30%) that green performance management practices enable them do their jobs effectively and efficiently. They also hold strongly that green performance management practices provide for continuous training Programmes for them and their staff members within their respective ministries. For instance, 36% of them agreed while 27% of them strongly agreed that green management practices lead to continuous training programme for staff members. Meanwhile, a very significant percentage of them at 45% and 27% agree and strongly agree respectively that Green Performance management practices provide for knowledge on matters concerning the environmental development in with ministry staff members. While 66% of them agreed that the green knowledge/ skills acquired from green training can be applied at workplace, 27% strongly agreed to it. These justify the acceptability of the green performance management practices among the staff members in the selected ministries of the federal civil service.

DISCUSSION

It was observed that the members of the staff studied decried the recruitment processes of their respective offices, which they perceived to be non-transparent. They seem to suggest that the recruitment exercises are not always objective which is part of the green performance practices. The study further established the need for staff motivation as many of them strongly averred that motivation is critical for increased performance of the staff members. It is also impressive to note that quite a good percentage of them agreed (45%) and strongly agreed (27%) that they participate in their green performance practices, such as staff appraisals, promotions, and trainings. These were further validated by more responses, where majority of the workers in the selected ministries, also agreed (66%) and strongly agreed (27%) that they are regularly appraised for promotions and advancements to enable them progress in their various cadres.

In terms of the level of use of balanced scorecard methodology among the selected ministries, the study was able to discover that there is a very minimal use of the balanced scorecard methodology among the ministries as majority of the staff members disagreed (27%) and also strongly disagreed (45%) that the balanced score card is operational in their ministries. Instead, majority of them (98%) strongly agreed that their ministries mainly utilize other performance evaluation measures apart from the balanced scorecard methodology. However, majority of them also strongly agree (66%) and agree (27%) that the ministry usually measures staff performance, while almost all of them hold strongly (94%) that the ministry measures its overall performance.

This paper established, among others, that green performance management practices enable the staff members to do their jobs effectively and efficiently as a significant percentage of them agreed (33%) and strongly agreed

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(30%) to it. It was also sacrosanct in this work that green performance management practices provide for continuous training programmes for them and their staff members. For instance, 36% of them agreed while 27% of them strongly agreed to the assertion. Meanwhile, a very significant percentage of them at 45% and 27% agree and strongly agree respectively that green performance management practices provide for knowledge on matters concerning the environmental development in the ministry. However, given that 66% of them agreed that the green knowledge/ skills acquired from green training can be applied at workplace, also 27% strongly agreed to it, quite a justification that there is an acceptable level of acceptability of the green performance management practices among the staff members in the selected ministries of the federal civil service.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that green performance management practices is very critical in any given establishment and that the use of balanced scorecard is still very minimal in the federal ministries studied, even though there are other evaluation measures for accessing the staff performance and overall output of the ministry.

The study also concludes that the staff members especially the management level workers should ensure adequate integration of the green performance management practices in the respective ministries to boost productivity and efficiency.

IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The recruitment processes of the ministry need to be transparent, and the right caliber of workers should always be engaged for efficiency.

The study further recommends for a more rewarding green practice of recognizing the staff members who distinguish themselves in various ways. This is also a part of staff motivation which should be of utmost concern for achieving a healthier work environment.

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